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**Gender Inequality and Emergence of Workforce
In Colonial Oron Society, 1885-1960**

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PRESS**Abstract**

The period 1900s-1960s is viewed as the age of colonialism of the African continent, which has been essentially structured and tempered with by historical processes. Significantly, gender inequality emerged during this period as a fundamental force for exploiting and stratifying African societies such as Oron. Gender inequality therefore became the hall-mark of the colonial plan to create and impose European socio-cultural influences on Africa. Consequently, male gender privileges and occupations became essential parts of colonial ethos enshrined in the culture of modernity while female gender was relegated especially in the colonial work-force contrary to the pre-colonial order in Africa. The study employs historical tools of qualitative analysis garnered from data obtained from primary and secondary sources. Women pre-colonial ingenuity capable of advancing economic, political and social progress were relegated and disregarded by the colonial authority while men only were allowed the rights to offices and industries.

Keywords: Gender, Oron Society, Inequality, Colonial period, Workforce

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INTRODUCTION

The concept of gender inequality denotes the social, political and cultural phenomenon in which a section of human, are treated unequally on ground of sex or gender. Such unequal treatments are accentuated by cultural, biological and psychological and social norms and traditions in the society. In the colonial, the concept and practice of gender inequality was entrenched in Oron society in particular and Africa generally by the colonial administration in workplaces, offices, social and religious environments to enhance avoidance of social and cultural problems associated with Oron indigenous practices. The white people were somewhat afraid of Oron socio-cultural practices and laws protecting African wives against adultery especially with *mmatang* (Whiteman). They never wanted to be inflicted with such agony resulting from canal knowledge of African women in offices and workplaces. The nearest way of escape was discriminating against them in the colonial workforce to dissuade and make women lost interest.

They were terrified over the African practices like *ekpo nka owo* practised in the neighbouring Ibibio country. This was the more

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reason they (Europeans) commissioned white missionaries to preach, soften and undermine indigenous practices which were life threatening, morally-oriented and superior in compliance and practice.

Gender inequality especially in workplace existed in every society to a certain degree but in conformity with norms of the people. The prevailing traditional occupations in the pre-colonial Oron society included farming, hunting, fishing, trading, brace work, black-smiting, weaving etc. Nyong (2023) adds that the occupations were generously practised by male and female without discrimination, though the females formed such occupational workforce under the guidance and leadership of male kins.

On his own part, Osung (2023) narrates that women were hardly alone or without the guidance of men except in few religious practices such as *ndem* priesthood or *salamanda* (water gods and goddess) where they acted as priests. This particular situation showed relative subordination of female to the male gender in area of occupational practices. It is true that Oron culture placed leadership role on men and allowed them to

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work under men without the feeling of bias, discrimination and disaffection, thereby showing how in the pre-colonial period, Oron women had reasonable powers and influence in various levels of the societies. Atim Emusi (2023) notes that in order to checkmate the excesses against women, a social group called *iban isong* or *mmani isong* (Women of the land) existed to help control and protect women against inequality, discrimination in the pre-colonial indigenous workforce. She asserted that such practices were halted and destroyed following the emergence of the superior force of colonialism which rendered women segregated against employments and other services.

Oron: Location and People

The Oron land and people consists of nine clans viz: Okpo, Uquong, Ebughu, Ibighi, Oki-Uso, Idua (Ilue), Efifat, Ubodung, Etta. However, due to geopolitical restructuring and creation of Akwa Ibom State, Oron nation has become fragmented into five (5) Local Government Areas of Udung Uko, Oron, Urue Offong Oruko, Mbo and Okobo.

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Oron people popularity described as one of the nations in the Old Calabar kingdom shares some form of ancestral relationships with the Eket, Ibeno and Eastern Obolo groups in Akwa Ibom State and the Adoni people of Rivers State. Oron is one of the major ethnic groups in Akwa Ibom State (Ibibio, Anang and Oron).

Oron nation is located in the south eastern fringe of Akwa Ibom State bounded in the South by Ibeno and the Atlantic Ocean, in the West by Esit Eket and Nsit Ubium, in the North by Nsit Atai and Uruan and in the east by the Cross River estuary.

Emergence Of Gender Inequality In Workforce

Gender inequality occurred in Oron following the advent of colonialism which destroyed the indigenous socio-cultural, economic and governance systems. Patriarchal policies and demonization of the pre-colonial Oron systems were imposed to justify the obnoxious policy (Shifteng, 2023). From the beginning of colonialism, the colonizers punctured and destroyed Oron indigenous societies with their obnoxious laws and reforms which caused women to be treated as inferior even

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in their marital homes, families of birth and places of work and therefore provided that men must be the exclusive occupants of positions of power and authority (Oyewumi, 1998:800).

In the colonial era, Oron and other African women were only known for child bearing. Women were neither renowned, distinguished nor admired. She could only be seen through the man and was not to be heard. Man was inherently superior to woman in all ramifications. The existence of women depended completely on men because in most cases, some customary laws treated women as minors. In most African societies, a woman must obtain the husband's consent to open or have access to bank account (Kunt, Kalpper, Singer, Ansar and Hess, 2018). Since the advent of colonialism in African, the feminine gender (women) became subjected to varying forms of discrimination and unequal treatments. Until early 1960s, it was difficult to find women as academic staff or teachers in one of the oldest scholars in Nigeria: Methodist Boys High School, Oron founded in 1905 by the Methodist Mission of Scotland. Also, in colonial companies like Elder Dempster and Mchiever which had their

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offices in the coastal fringes of Oron, it was completely out of place to find women as staff in whatever capacity (Edet, 2013)

Reasons for gender inequality in the colonial period

Colonial factor:

The colonial conception of gender conspicuously marginalized the women-folk, while it privileged men. Since cultural imperialism viewed Eurocentric religion, ideas and morals as innately superior to those of the indigenous African societies, the resultant changes brought about by this imperial summation were ofcourse, noticeable in relations between both sexes in the continent. Colonialism visibly enabled the imposition of rigid roles including gender perceptions, on our collective consciousness. This perception explains how historical dominance of Africa by Europe became the major, reason for oppression, servitude and marginalization of the African women.

Economic factor:

This supposedly accounts for the origin of the emergence of inequality of in workforce against female gender in Oron society. Trade and economic reason centered on exploitation of

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the people and their resources for the development of European industries and economies became the cardinal reason for colonialism. As a result, Oron women in particular and African women in general were seen as “weaker sex” and socio-cultural agents of white man’s death, hence, they were excluded from colonial workforce in coal mines, railways, postal services, church administration, army and colonial work-force. They were only used as palm oil and kernel nut carriers by the middlemen who were intermediaries between the interior and coasts of Oron, Efik and Uruan (Katrin: 2013).

Furthermore, the introduction of monetized economy which consequently subjected the people to peasantization and proleternization through forced labour has adversely affected chances of Oron women. According to Keesing (1985) those activities which required sheer physical strength of the shoulder and arms as well as those activities which required much mobility belonged to the masculine domain while less rigorous activities such as carrying of loads, weeding, nursing and cooking were allowed for the women.

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With heavy pangs of anger over discrimination in workforce, constant harassment and imposition of taxation on them during the indirect rule policy of the British colonial administration in Nigeria, the Women War of 1929 took place in Ikot Abasi in the present day Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. The protest was a nationalistic attempt by women to repel and rise against inequality in workforce, exploitation and imposition of colonial laws and taxes on men and women (Eluwa, Ukagwu, Nwachukwu and Nwaubuni 1988).

It must be emphasized that even in the military arm of colonialism, no African woman was recruited yet African women such as Queen Amina of Zaria, Queen Nzinga Mbande (Lica 40BC), (c.1583-1663) of Mbundi in Angola, Queen Nnanny (c.1685-c.1750) of Jamaica, Yaa Asantewa (c. 1840-1921) of Ashanti, Moremi of Ife, the 1929 Ikot Abasi women rioters and Emotan of the ancient Benin were great African female warriors and leaders (Pitchon, 2022).

Oron (African) Socio-cultural and Religious Factors:

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When the colonizers began to nurse interests in Africa, they sent their ‘foot-soldiers’ personified as discoverers, missionaries and agents of imperialism to carry out studies on Africa societies. Consequently, those colonial agents reports were unanimously on their assertions that African (Oron) women were harbingers of evil, misfortune and capable of inflicting sickness and death against white men who would dare to have any immoral interest or relationship.

As earlier asserted by Talbot(1918), the white people were scared of the laws and traditions protecting the women against the randy and promiscuous lifestyle of the European workers and administrators. Such practices as *ekpo nkawo* among the Ibibio and *ulukolor* among the Oron people were seen as death-traps by the white-people *mmatang*, hence, the stringent discriminatory policy which secluded women from equal working opportunity with men.

Effects Of Gender Inequality In Workforce In The Colonial Period

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Colonialism and its policies had far-reaching consequences due to rigid gender inequality in workforce against the African women. These consequences have received little or no effort aimed at correcting them in the post-colonial male-dominated law making institutions and governments in Africa.

Due to ages of neglect and discrimination in workforce against women, they had no option other than resorting to mass movement or migration to urban centres where they are engaged in commercial sex works, to be able to survive.

Again, a number of African women have found employments in the formal sector such as petty trading, commodity production like soap, garri etc and retailing of food and liquor. Even in those attempts to survive under those informal and subsistence economic activities and migration, they were strictly policed and harassed by different colonial administrations.

CONCLUSION

With the advent of colonialism and its ravenous desire to exploit Africa through trade and economic interests, the emergence and

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application of gender inequality was witnessed rigidly in almost all the spheres or areas of African life especially in the colonial workforce.

Though inequality between genders is a natural phenomenon which affects both men and women, yet the extent of emergence and application of the capitalist oriented gender inequality in workforce had witnessed overall economic stagnation, indignity and hindrance of the process of social change toward a better Africa continent. Infact, it was slavery in another form.

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